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Abstract: It is known that education is the process of conveying information of certain social importance to the younger generation. In a preschool educational institution, it is carried out in the classroom, on walks, in games, in communication with parents, etc. One of the most ancient types of human activity - child education has undergone significant changes during its centuries-old history of development, from a daily process to a complex of scientifically based systematic interaction based on the results of creative and creative activity. It is necessary to learn to manage the pedagogical process in a preschool educational institution under the conditions of introducing pedagogical technologies in the process. These processes were also studied in the article.

Key words: management, management, result, management hierarchy, management culture, pedagogical management, conscious creative work, result-based management, improving educational efficiency.

At the meeting held on August 16, 2017 under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, important tasks were set for the structural reform of the preschool education system and the full inclusion of children in these institutions. As a result of the analyzes in this regard, a number of major documents were issued in a short period of time. Decree No. PF-5198 "On radical improvement measures" and Decision No. PQ-3305 "On organization of activities of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan" were adopted. In fact, the initial stage of education is kindergarten, where the child receives moral lessons, experiences communication with adults and peers, reveals his creative potential in games, teamwork, and elementary skills in educational activities. acquires skills. We studied the management of the pedagogical process in a preschool educational institution in the context of the introduction of pedagogical technologies and created a management model. The algorithm of management actions based on the created model of managing the pedagogical process unites the team of teachers, parents and children in a single educational space that ensures children's age-appropriate development and emotional well-being. The core of the proposed model is the manager's management actions that bring dynamic, positive changes to the organization of the pedagogical process at the stage of introducing pedagogical technologies in a preschool educational institution.

Our society is changing very quickly. The direction of our country towards changes in the economy, political and social life requires changes in all other institutions of society. In such conditions, it is necessary to pay special attention to management - management experience of the developed countries of the world. But it is practically impossible to transfer management models from one socio-cultural environment to another, because management is determined by a combination of factors. The form of management, type of ownership and level of market development are different. Therefore, the gradual introduction of management in our country should be carried out in systematic cooperation with the mentioned factors. There are three types of management tools: leadership, organization, management hierarchy. The main tool here is to influence a person from above (stimulating, planning, organizing and controlling activity, as well

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as using the main functions of distribution, wealth, etc.). The second is management culture, which includes a set of values, social norms, attitudes, behaviors developed and recognized by society, organization, group of people. And the third one is the market, market relations, these. is management based on the sale and purchase of products and services, the balance of the interests of the seller and the buyer.

Orientation of the educational organization to high performance indicators represents a number of requirements for the appropriate level of management. Based on new approaches to the management of the preschool education system, a modern director should have the qualities of a competent specialist, as well as a high professional culture of communication and ethical standards. Today, there are various preschool education organizations in the preschool education system, improved pedagogical technologies and methods have emerged, is being used in practice, innovative activities are becoming popular. Mainly, the directions and requirements of preschool education are being changed. That is why we need a director of a new generation who can solve educational problems at a modern level.

The task of forming a child's personality - a preschool teacher - is most successfully carried out when the management actions of the head of the preschool educational institution are combined with the teachers' desire to provide pedagogical support and improvement to the child in his development and formation. working methods, implementation of the educational institution's own management concept. Implementation of such a concept largely depends on the set of management principles. "Principles of management are the basic rules that guide the management entity in its activities and implement it in certain socio-economic conditions." The analysis of special literature and the experience of organizing the pedagogical process in a preschool educational institution made it possible to distinguish the following principles of management: goal setting, complexity, democratization, psychologization of teaching and upbringing models. All these principles are a guide for action in a developing and developing preschool and form the basis of updating its activities.

Summary

In recent decades, fundamental changes have taken place in the preschool education system, which have had a significant impact on the problems of teaching, upbringing and management at this stage of the educational institution's development. Literally 5-6 years ago, preschool educational institutions were on the verge of survival, but major changes in regulatory, administrative, and economic conditions made it possible to modernize all aspects of preschool education. There is a clear tendency for pre-school educational institutions to search for meaningful directions and unique forms of education that allow them to find their image, to find enthusiasm in their work. The unification of pre-school educational institutions, which was customary until recently, was replaced by the diversity of their types, the diversity of curricula and programs, and the introduction of new technologies. The current guidelines for the modernization of the Russian education system - availability, quality, efficiency - place increasing demands on preschool educational institutions. Organization of the development of the preschool education system is possible only with the development of innovations that contribute to qualitative changes in the activities of preschool educational institutions and are expressed in their qualitative transition to a new stage - the development mode.

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